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ПЕРІОДУ У ХВОРИХ ЯКІ ПЕРЕНЕСЛИ МОЗКОВИЙ ІШЕМІЧНИЙ
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**PECULIARITIES OF THE EARLY RECOVERY PERIOD IN
PATIENTS WITH CEREBRAL ISCHEMIC STROKE, DEPENDING ON
THE PRESENCE OF TYPE 2 DIABETES**

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Cerebral ischemic stroke (CIS) is one of the leading problems of modern angioneurology. Every year, more than 20 million people have strokes and about 7 million people die. Type 2 diabetes (T2D) increases the risk of stroke by 2-6 times.

Aim of the research: To analyze the features of the early recovery period in patients with CIS depending on the presence of T2D. For that purpose next goals were set: 1)To conduct a comparative analysis of the dynamics of neurological deficit in patients with CIS in the early recovery period, depending on the presence of T2D. 2)To study the effect of T2D on the course of the early recovery period in patients with CIS. 3)Evaluate the effectiveness of a comprehensive rehabilitation program in patients with CIS.

Materials and methods: 41 patients with CIS in the early recovery period of the disease were examined on the basis of Zaporizhzhya City Hospital № 6 of the angioneurological center. The average patient's age was (61.1 ± 9.8) years. Patients have divided: into the main group - patients with CIS and T2D ($n = 20$, average age $62,5 \pm 8,5$) and the comparison group – patients with CIS without T2D ($n=21$, average age $59 \pm 10,9$). All patients were clinically and neurologically examined using modern scales – NIHSS, mRS. The diagnosis of CIS was based on a complex clinical-neurological at the time of admission to the neurorehabilitation department and at the time of discharge from the hospital and computed tomographic study of the brain during the acute period of the disease.

Results: A comparative assessment of the clinical course of CIS in patients with T2D and without T2D. The use of comprehensive rehabilitation measures in the early recovery period showed worse recovery of impaired functions in the main

group of patients. According to the NIHSS scale, 9(45%) patients had a mild stroke in the main group (statue on NIHSS ≤ 5 points), a statue on NIHSS 6-14 points (n=11(55%) - mild to moderately severe stroke. In the comparison group, 15(71,4%) patients had mild stroke (statue on NIHSS ≤ 5 points), statue on NIHSS 6-14 points (n=6(28,6%) - mild to moderately severe stroke. At the beginning of the early recovery period, there were significant differences between patients of clinical groups on the NIHSS scale (6.5 ± 2.8 points, 4.2 ± 2.7 points, $p < 0.05$) and mRS scale (respectively, 2.9 ± 0.7 points, 2.2 ± 0.7 points, $p < 0.05$). After the rehabilitation course, there was a positive dynamics in neurological status, on the NIHSS scale: the main group 5.1 ± 2.5 points, the comparison group 2.8 ± 2.3 points ($p < 0.05$) The degree of disability and functional disorders in patients with CIS with T2D and CIS without T2D on the mRS scale significantly decreased (2.7 ± 0.7 points; 1.6 ± 0.8 points, ($p < 0.01$). All patients were prescribed comprehensive rehabilitation treatment according to modern protocols.

Conclusions:

- 1) We found that patients with CIS and T2D had more severe neurological deficits according to the NIHSS and mRS scales.
- 2) It was found that during rehabilitation treatment, T2D negatively affected the recovery processes in patients who underwent CIS.